

Thank you to Professor Nina: An Inspiring Teacher, A Mentor, A Challenger and an Awesome Researcher

Dr. Waqas Ikram*

**R&D Team Manager at ABB AS. Ole Deviks Vei 10, Oslo, Norway*

Abstract: Prof. Nina Thornhill was Waqas' university teacher at University College London where she was teaching MENG students. Waqas had the pleasure of both being taught by Nina and to conduct his master's degree project under her supervision. Waqas' interests in the field of wireless sensor networks and Nina's enthusiasm to explore new avenues of research led to a successful collaborative project between University College London and Imperial College London. Later, when Nina moved to Imperial College London, an opportunity came up for a PhD position in wireless process automation which Waqas undertook under Nina's supervision. Nina's extensive knowledge and industry experience was invaluable throughout Waqas' time under her supervision. Many academic papers have been published based on their joint work and many presentations delivered at various prestigious forums and conferences. Moreover, Nina's position as ABB/Royal Academy of Engineering Chair of Process Engineering provided an opportunity for Waqas to bring his research into ABB. After his university education, he joined ABB as a scientist, and now leads an R&D team developing solutions for new challenges facing energy industries.

Keywords: ABB, supervisor, ABB Royal Academy of Engineering Chair.

Nina's association with Waqas goes back many years. In the years 2004-08, Nina was a teacher in University College London (UCL). She was teaching MENG students and supervising master's students projects. Nina was Waqas' supervisor. Nina was well known in the student community as a well-disciplined and inspiring teacher who challenges students to think outside-the-box and find innovative solutions to research challenges. This has motivated her students to be their best. Waqas' master's project was one such example, where a joint project was conducted in collaboration between two universities. Waqas really appreciates her effort and unending support in this regard.

During Waqas' research at Imperial College London (ICL), Nina's expertise in control theory, instrumentation and condition monitoring was invaluable. What her students found was that Nina has written short articles and papers on topics which are often hard to grasp in first instance. This was very helpful to students preparing for exams. Her academic contributions are well known and documented. One aspect which may not be obvious is her mentorship. Despite her busy schedule, she always made time for her students, assisted them in challenging times and her friendliness makes every student feel special.

Till this day, Nina tries to connect her or her affiliates research to relevant parties and stakeholders. Which often leads to new projects and research venture between companies and universities.

Teaching is a skill that is unique. Whether it is about simplifying difficult topics with simple real-world analogies, or by borrowing equipment from other universities, bringing in experts or collaborating with industry inside or outside the UK, Nina goes beyond conventional means to teach students and fellow researchers.

For all the great time spent in two universities (2004-2012), it was a privilege being Nina's student. Nina has influenced Waqas' life in such a positive way that words cannot express his appreciation. From the bottom of his heart, he thanks her and appreciates all she has done and wishing her the best in future endeavours.

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